
A Review of the Challenges and Prospects for Educational Development amidst National Insecurity in Nigeria: The Socio Philosophical Way Forward

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ABSTRACT

The goal of education in modern times is broader than it was in preliterate communities. Education currently influences politics, society, family, and the economy, among other things. Education must evolve in tandem with society, which is continuously changing and evolving. In the Nigerian context, professionals both at home and abroad have voiced great worry about the incoherence or inadequacies of the country's education system, particularly at the college, polytechnic, and university levels. Youth between the ages of 18 and 30 years are commonly implicated in numerous crimes that contribute to insecurity. This paper applied a theoretical approach to periscope the multi-layered challenges of insecurity in Nigeria, particularly as these challenges impact the Nigerian nation's educational trajectory with its associated negative consequences for Nigerian youth in particular and the country's future in general. The paper also examined various literature materials to evaluate the results of previous publications on the topic under review, and thus recommended that government at all levels and stakeholders in Nigeria's education industry be more retrospective, introspective and proactive on issues of national security in order to arrest the negative drift that is currently affecting Nigeria's educational projections.

Keywords: Education, Insecurity, Philosophy and National Development.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a process through which individuals are formerly encouraged to adequately direct and supervise the development of their talents for both personal and societal benefits (Okeke, 2003). The aims of education are to develop individuals to live effectively and efficiently in society in order to contribute to its growth and uplifting. As a consequence, through education, the behavioural patterns of people can be influenced in the desired direction. According to Matawal (2007), efforts on the part of the successive administrations

in Nigeria to encourage education and the development of the country's human resources base have been developed through various policies and programs. Often times, there is failure on the part of educational reform to offer broad-based education in the growth of the mind, comprehension of the environment, and development of relevant skills, talents, and competencies to co-exist with and contribute to the development of society. Nevertheless, without national security, prospecting for national development is worthless. Simply put, a nation without security is a danger to its educational development. There exists a relationship between national security and educational development. At present, the major concern in the society is national security. This has been a national problem that concerns all stakeholders in the Nigeria State which requires the full and devoted participation of all groups and interests that makes up the Nigeria society. National security is not defined by military and defense strength; it is a bit broader than that. The restriction on the definition of national security set out the foundation for the disproportionate budgetary allocation of funds to secure the protection of lives and property at the expense of other equally essential sectors of the economy that are directly or indirectly related to national security.

National security, according to Redia (2011), is defined as a state's ability to overcome any sort of difficulty, regardless of the problem. He argues that national security includes not only military strength, defense, or law enforcement, but more fundamental elements such as employment, water, and food security. We can say at this juncture that a national security policy would be useless to the unemployed and hungry individuals who make up the bulk of the population in an impoverished country like ours. For the all-encompassing nature of the term "national security", the former U.S President, Barrack Obama, in 2010 considered a holistic worldview in his definition of America's national security interests as " a strong, innovative, and growing U.S economy in an open International economic system that promotes opportunity and prosperity. Likewise, Abubakar (2005) argued that

the present international talks on national security specified the need to appreciate security as “the fight to get the most essentials of existence such as food, fuel, medicine, and shelter.” From the point of view of human physiological requirements, security is critical for achieving physical and national security, as well as general peace and development because social dissatisfaction caused by the lack of qualitative basic-human security might lead to security in different socio-economic conflicts. Besides socio-economic security difficulties, some of the main security concerns affecting the nation are political and electioneering conflicts, ethno-religious crises, ethnic militias, border disputes, cultism, criminality, and organized crime (Abubakar, 2005).

Statement of Problem and Objective of Study

The primary objective of this study is to show that a major gap still exist between the security architecture of the Federal Government of Nigeria and the continued absence of appropriate national security frame needed for the protection of lives and properties of Nigerians in general and students population in general. For example, the terrorist organization Jama'atu Ahlis Sunna Lidda'awati wal-Jihad, also known as Boko Haram, which in Hausa translates as “Western education is banned,” executed violent assaults from 2009 to the 2013-2017 period in an attempt to set up a radical Islamic government. Boko Haram announced its allegiance to 'IS' in March 2015, renaming them the “Islamic State West Africa.” Boko Haram's violence is against people and attacks on schools. Human Rights Watch revealed that over 10,000 people died in Nigeria as a result of Boko Haram's insurgents, between 2009 and early 2016. The Nigerian Senate later declared a state of emergency in Adamawa, Borno, and Yobe states in May 2013, resulting in heightened military operations and an upsurge in violence. The report from the International Organization for Migration revealed that 1,757,288 persons were displaced in Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba, and Yobe states in August 2017, a modest reduction from prior estimates. The majority of the Internally Displaced Persons (IDP) population (80 percent) lived in Borno state, with insurgency

being the main cause of dislocation. Boko Haram banned thousands of children in Borno and Yobe states from finishing their education by destroying schools, displacing community members, and abducting female students on a large scale and committing other crimes. As submitted by the UN (2017), the United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), over three million children in northeastern Nigeria are in desperate need of education.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Philosophical Meaning of Education

Education is used to denote activities, processes or enterprises of educating. As an activity or process, education, consists of cultivating certain dispositions and these dispositions include skills, abilities, knowledge, attitude, belief, values and character. Therefore, education as a phenomenon that is concerned with the development of personality. This description is in line with societal assumption about education. The societal assumption about education is that when one is educated, such a person has undergone a personality development orientation programme. A closer observation of the curriculum of educational pursuit in most societies portrays a complete tendency towards personality development. Education also emphasizes the development of individuals and concerns itself with providing total mental, physical and vocational development of human persons. With this understanding, education can be defined as the "totality of mental, physical, psychological, social and the overall development of the individual others and the society at large.

The Benefits of Education to Mankind

Promotes physical and mental health.

Helps people to be well informed.

Helps people to acquire the knowledge and skills needed in order to solve the various problems of life.

Promotes fullest personality through maximum use of the natural gift or intellectual, manual and artistic skills

Cultivate high degree of intelligence and help to apply it reasonably well in order to promote balanced judgment in whatever one does. Develops good values and attitudes like honesty, good- neighborliness, self-disciplines, etc.

Historicizing Education in Nigeria

Before the introduction of Western education, traditional education was widely practiced in Nigeria. According to Fafunwa (1974), the underlying objectives of the traditional education system were to develop the child's physical skills, character, and respect for elders and authority figures. It also aimed to foster intellectual abilities, provide vocational training, cultivate a positive attitude towards honest labor, instill a sense of belonging, and encourage active participation. Several scholars, including Fafunwa (1974), Taiwo (1980), Ozigi (1981), and Adesina (1988), have extensively documented the history of Western education in Nigeria. The roots of Western education in Nigeria can be traced back to the 15th century when Portuguese traders arrived in Benin. Initially, the education provided by these traders was limited to the sons of the Oba of Benin and his chiefs. However, the formal establishment of Western education in Nigeria began in 1842 with the arrival of Christian missionaries from the Wesleyan Methodist Society. They established a Christian mission in Badagry, near Lagos, which was later relocated to Abeokuta. Along with building a mission house and a church, they also established a school. The influence of the Catholic Mission Society and the Presbyterian Mission played a significant role in shaping Nigeria's educational landscape. Subsequently, the Nigerian government intervened and took control of the mission schools. This led to a diverse ownership structure, where elementary and secondary schools, as well as post-secondary institutions, came under the ownership of the Federal Government, State Governments, Local Governments, religious organizations, and private individuals. This transition sets the stage for a discussion on Nigerian education and its relationship with national security.

Education and National Security In Nigeria

The relationship between education and security is complex and could have either positive or negative effects, depending on the specific circumstances. Recognizing this connection is crucial as it enables individuals, organizations, countries, and the human species as a whole to explore, appreciate, comprehend, and improve their physical and social environments. A broad perspective on various issues, rather than a narrow and limited one, can only be achieved through a well-rounded education. Alemika, (2016) argued, that education plays a vital role in fostering tolerance towards different religions, beliefs, cultures, and limitations, thus promoting social harmony and security. It also empowers individuals to listen to diverse viewpoints without losing their composure or self-esteem. Many of the conflicts witnessed in the human society stems from ignorance and the manipulation of ethnic and religious identities and factors. True education, which extends beyond the confines of traditional schooling, nurtures individuals that are tolerant, respectful, and capable of understanding and coexisting with people from diverse ethnic, economic, religious, cultural, and other identity backgrounds.

Orikpe (2013) noted that analyzing the theme of "security", is worthless without the presence of adequate education. It is not surprising, however, that education, when properly transmitted and applied, has the potential to promote national security (Radda, 2013). Yet, if education is not properly promoted, the unskilled and uneducated jobless adolescents will be readily drawn to a variety of social crimes, leading to across the country. The absence of education or a poor level of education is far more damaging if such education is not directed towards self-reliance which implies a type of education that creates employment opportunities and enabling environment for Nigerian youth seeking economic engagements. As regards what the future holds for the youths, the educated ones have a brighter future than those who are uneducated and have not learned any skill. Youth who lack or have limited access to education are susceptible to being recruited as thugs, rebels, and terrorists through indoctrination,

highlighting the inherent insecurity associated with a lack of education (Alemika, 2016). Inadequate education also poses a threat to national security, as evidenced by the significant increase in youth unemployment, which reflects the flawed assumptions of the Nigerian educational system. For example, Akwara et al. (2013) revealed that in 2008, 15% of the Nigerian workforce was unemployed, and by 2011, this proportion had risen to 20%. The most affected group by this situation is the youth, who experience the highest rates of unemployment in the country. The scholars further established a link between unemployment and poverty. Jega (2002) argued that the large number of unemployed youths in Nigeria's rural and urban areas, facing the temptation and opportunity for looting that often precedes riots and revenge attacks, require little motivation or mobilization to engage in such violent acts. Poverty and unemployment, therefore, appear to be significant contributing factors to Nigeria's violent conflicts.

Highlighting the connection between education and national security, Akinwumi (2004) asserts that Nigeria's education system has promoted rural-urban mobility, leading many young people to migrate to different urban centers in search of non-existent employment. Consequently, they find themselves battling disappointment and frustration in their struggle to survive, often resorting to criminal activities. Unemployment has now become a catalyst for the country's increasing violence and disorder. The combination of unemployment and poverty creates a fertile ground for actions that pose a threat to national security. The rise in crime directly correlates with unemployment and poverty. In the predominantly Quranic education-focused northern region of Nigeria, where poverty is prevalent, the ability to think broadly is restricted. This situation sets the stage for insurgency, which represents the most significant threat to Nigeria's security. Poverty and inequality contribute to violence, with 90% of all violence-related deaths occurring in economically disadvantaged nations, and poorer neighborhoods in cities often becoming high-crime areas (Awake in

Akwarā, Akwarā, Enwuchola, Adekunle, & Uđaw, 2013). Similarly, Akande & Okuwa (2009) argue that youth unemployment significantly contributes to conflicts experienced in Africa, particularly in Nigeria. The current socio-economic climate pushes students to seek livelihoods through conflict, crime, and violence. Despite the severity of the situation, the knowledge acquired through education can be utilized to reverse this prevalent negative trend.

METHODOLOGY

This paper adopted a theoretical and systematic analysis approach including a review of previously published papers to investigate and integrate relevant details concerning the topic under discussion. It also applied secondary data which included magazines, newspapers, websites, and government documents for its findings, conclusion and recommendations. This study may eventually serve as an antecedent to elaborate future research.

DISCUSSION AND FINDINGS

Nigeria has been experiencing internal insecurity particularly from 2007 to the present, and it appears to be illusive. Among the few signs of insecurity in Nigeria are ethno-religious disputes, murder, abduction, and terrorism. Insecurity in Nigeria takes different forms, ranging from varied areas in Nigeria. For example, between 1999 and 2007, militants in the Niger Delta region (South-South) fought with oil corporations in the area, killing and damaging oil companies and Federal Government properties in the process. The Hausa and indigenes in Jos, Plateau State (North Central), have been at odds since roughly 2002. Kidnapping, ritual killing, and armed robbery are also instances of instability in the South-East, as they have been in the South-West. The Boko Haram insurgency has been the largest threat to internal security in the North-East, North-West, and North-Central of Nigeria since 2009. Again, the youth are not left out of these insecurity challenges. They are significant figures in the war against crime in all of these examples of insecurity.

These categories of youths are classified as either unemployed, unemployable, impoverished, or dissatisfied because they are being deprived of the obligatory education, or they are educated but yet unemployed. It is unavoidable for poor youths to counter the urge to commit crime if doing so will allow them to fulfill their immediate material needs. Simply put, education and national security are inseparably entwined. This supports Abugu's argument (as cited in Abayomi, Youdeowei & Uwandu (2016) that "Nigeria's strength, security, and well-being are all dependent on the quality of its education".

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Philosophy is an intellectual activity which seeks understanding of the most complex systems of reality and human experience. The question of the relevance of philosophy to humanity elicits different narratives about its usefulness. While the West leverages philosophy for the all round development of the human personality and the human society, Sub-Saharan Africa still views philosophy with suspicion as too technical and abstract to be of use to engage with concrete problems of human existence. Through the broad theme on philosophy and human affairs. This paper attempted to make conscious effort to interrogate the various narratives highlighted in the areas of the connections between education national security and the contribution of philosophy as an academic discipline. The end in view is to emphasize the relevant and efficacy of positive philosophical engagement in the reordering of the human society. Consequently, it is not excusable for the for the various levels of government in Nigeria not to afford the need of develop a well coordinated preventative action plan to keep Nigeria's educational institutions safe and secure as well ensure vigilance against socio-psychological security challenges. Different levels of government in Nigeria must apply a zero-tolerance approach to any challenge to the security of lives and properties in schools, including attacks on school buildings as a result of conflict and war. The application of state of the art and digitalized security technologies should also be prioritized especially in providing safety to students and educational

infrastructures across the country as a way of guaranteeing that student rights are protected.

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